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**BEYOND INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY
PROTECTION: OTHER AI INTELLECTUAL
PROPERTY STRATEGIES FOR THE
AFRICAN CONTEXT**

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Beyond intellectual property protection: Other AI intellectual property strategies for the African context*

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I. Introduction

The significance of intellectual property (IP) to artificial intelligence (AI) has been widely recognised. IP has played and continues to play a prominent role in the development and deployment of AI in many parts of the world including on the African continent.¹ As systems to protect creative and inventive outputs, the relevance of IP rights to AI is not in doubt.² Indeed, the discourse on AI and IP is focused on viewing AI from two key aspects/perspectives: as legal objects and as legal subjects.³ As legal objects, AI systems are conceptualised or envisaged as tools with which specific objectives and specific tasks are achieved and undertaken respectively. In this regard, legal protection (in this case, IP protection) is sought and acquired for the AI systems or for the AI itself and perhaps, outputs generated using AI systems. Such IP protection could be patents, copyright or trade secrets, which is geared towards protecting the creative or inventive output embodied in the AI system.⁴ As legal subjects, AI is perceived (or conceived) as the legal subject or person acquiring rights to or

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¹ See 'WIPO Begins Public Consultation Process on Artificial Intelligence and Intellectual Property Policy', PR/2019/843 (13 December 2019) <https://www.wipo.int/pressroom/en/articles/2019/article_0017.html>. See also, 'Public Views on Artificial Intelligence and Intellectual Property Policy' (October, 2020) <https://www.uspto.gov/sites/default/files/documents/USPTO_AI-Report_2020-10-07.pdf>.

² Pillay, N., 2020. Artificial intelligence for Africa: An opportunity for growth, development, and democratization, p. 34-35. See also, Gervais, D., 2020. The Human Cause. In *Research Handbook on Intellectual Property and Digital Technologies*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

³ Lai, A., 2021. Artificial Intelligence, LLC: Corporate Personhood as Tort Reform. *Mich. St. L. Rev.*, p.597.

⁴ Aplin T and Pasqualetto G 'Artificial Intelligence and Copyright Protection' in Rosa Maria Ballardini, Petri Kuoppamäki, Olli Pitkänen (eds) *Regulating Industrial Internet Through IPR, Data Protection and Competition Law* (Kluwer, 2019), *King's College London Law School Research Paper*, chapter 5; Ballardini R.M, He K and Roos T 'AI-generated content: authorship and inventorship in the age of artificial intelligence' *Online Distribution of Content in the EU* (2019),117-135.

interests in a legal object (i.e., IP-protectable material) or engaging in creative endeavours or taking inventive steps.⁵ Both aspects have generated and continue to generate debate across Africa and the world on questions of law and regulations on AI relating to IP protection, ethics, privacy, competition, non-proliferation, etc.⁶

In the field of IP law which is the focus of this chapter, these questions (also) recognise and acknowledge both the challenges and opportunities that AI presents for Africa and African countries. Following from this, one popular proposal is to grant IP protection to AI systems and/or AI-generated products.⁷ The argument embodied in such proposal is that the statutory monopoly or exclusivity available due to IP protection would incentivise the development of more AI systems and/or tools. However, despite the benefits of such proposals, there is the important question of whether given the development goals and plans set by African countries for themselves, IP protection is necessary or desirable to promote or incentivise the development and deployment of AI systems. As used in this chapter, “necessity” or “desirability” means granting or proposing the grant of IP rights to protect or secure AI systems and incentivise further and increased development and deployment of AI in Africa. Necessity or desirability takes for granted the need to incentivise the development and deployment of AI in Africa and only considers whether an IP rights framework is needed or desirable to incentivise these works. This explains the title of this chapter: while the chapter argues that IP protection would be available for AI systems, it implies that the IP *system* is more than just IP protection.⁸ The chapter will argue, in other words, that the intellectual property system embodies other components that may be better placed to harness the opportunities and overcome the challenges of AI on the continent.

⁵ Comer A ‘AI: Artificial Inventor or the Real Deal?’ *North Carolina Journal of Law & Technology* 22:3 (2021), 447 at 472 – 473.

⁶ Ncube, C. and Rutenberg, I., 2021. Intellectual property and Fourth Industrial Revolution technologies1. *Leap 4.0. African Perspectives on the Fourth Industrial Revolution: African Perspectives on the Fourth Industrial Revolution*, p.393.

⁷ Gervais, D., 2020. The Human Cause. In *Research Handbook on Intellectual Property and Digital Technologies*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

⁸ See Chidede T ‘The Role of Intellectual Property Rights’ Protection in Advancing Development in South Africa’ *Law, Democracy and Development*, 26 (2022) 168 at 175-176 (arguing that “[t]he classical thought is that the rationale for protecting IPRs is to establish private rights in creations and innovations to grant control over their exploitation and provide an incentive for further creativity. While this is true, one should not overlook the ultimate goal of the public good – promoting progress for the benefit of society”).

Although relevant examples from other African countries are used, South Africa's National Development Plan 2030 (NDP 2030) is deployed as a backdrop for the analysis. The NDP 2030 embodies greater ownership and political control of the processes leading to its production and has the potential to influence the implementation of development priorities in a more effective way.⁹ Unlike the UN Sustainable Development Goals 2030 (SDGs) and the African Union Agenda 2063 which respectively express global and regional commitments and do not mention the peculiarities of any national context and national development challenges, the NDP explicitly and understandably seeks to address injustices resulting from South Africa's apartheid past.¹⁰ The overarching aim of the NDP 2030 is to eliminate poverty and reduce inequality by 2030.¹¹ Amongst the five notable trends indicated in the NDP 2030, technology features as a trend South Africa must understand and respond appropriately to in order to actualise its development goals.¹² On the whole, the NDP 2030 uses a system-based view of technology and innovation emphasising networks, public-private collaborations and regulatory coherence as key for technological advancement.¹³ Given the context of these national development plans or goals, the pertinent question that this chapter seeks to answer is how best the IP system could be applied to harness the opportunities of AI for Africa. The chapter is premised on the argument that the use of the IP system to take advantage of the opportunities, and overcome the challenges, of AI on the continent should be based on the recognition of the contextual characteristics that exist in the continent as embodied in expressed development plans.

Part II of this chapter takes a brief but closer look at South Africa's NDP 2030 highlighting the role of AI in the actualisation of the development goals. More significantly, Part II showcases the contextual characteristics of South Africa as a microcosm of the African continent to show how such context should necessitate a different AI IP policy. Part II concludes that the

⁹ Okitasari, M. and Katramiz, T., 2022. The national development plans after the SDGs: Steering implications of the global goals towards national development planning. *Earth System Governance*, 12, p.100136.

¹⁰ May J 'Integrating Human Rights Approach to Food Security in National Plan and Budget: The South African National Development Plan' In Ebenezer Durojaye and Gladys Mirugi-Mukundi, Exploring the link between poverty and human rights in Africa, *Pretoria University Law Press* (2020) chapter 2.

¹¹ 'National Development Plan 2030: Our future – make it work' <https://www.gov.za/sites/default/files/gcis_document/201409/ndp-2030-our-future-make-it-workr.pdf>

¹² See National Development Plan 2030, p. 28.

¹³ Jegede, O. and Ncube, C., 2021. Science, Technology, Innovation Management for Industrial Development in South Africa: Implications for The Fourth Industrial Revolution. *Science*, 15(9), p. 680.

imperative for South Africa and other African countries is to facilitate AI applications across all sectors of the economy. Such AI applications in health, education, governance, etc. will contribute to Africa's development. Part III builds from the preceding section and presents an overview of the varied uses of the IP systems (specifically, copyright and patent laws) to promote creativity; inventiveness and innovation. On this basis, this part supports the argument that the grant or conferment of IP rights is not the only way to facilitate investment and innovation in the AI space or to harness the opportunities of AI or address the challenges posed by AI. Rather, the IP system *also* offers scope delineation and exceptions to IP protection that can also (and perhaps better) facilitate investment and innovation in the AI space. Part IV then proposes strategies within the IP systems that can enable Africa to take advantage of the opportunities, and overcome the challenges, of AI on the continent. Part V concludes.

II. Contextualising AI for Africa: South Africa's National Development Plan 2030

In 2012, the South African government launched the NDP 2030 setting out key priorities for South Africa to meet the overarching aim of eliminating poverty and reducing inequality by 2030. The NDP 2030 was built on the basis of a 2011 Diagnostic Report prepared by the National Planning Commission, which sets out a number of challenges that South Africa must address including high rate of unemployment; quality of school education; underperforming health system; resource-intensive economy and inequality within the South African society.¹⁴ Building on the report, the NDP 2030 highlighted three priorities viz: "raising employment through faster economic growth; improving the quality of education, skills development and innovation; and building the capability of the state to play a developmental, transformative role".¹⁵

Other literature support this context of South Africa which persists in varying degrees over a decade since the adoption of the NDP 2030. There are still high levels of unemployment and

¹⁴ See National Planning Commission - Diagnostic Report 2011, <https://www.gov.za/sites/default/files/gcis_document/201409/npcdiagnosticoverview1.pdf>

¹⁵ See National Development Plan 2030, p. 27.

a majority of citizens lack both advanced and basic skills.¹⁶ Government's track record in policy implementation and private sector engagement remains poor.¹⁷ Similarly, government's position on the role of the private sector and the limits of private sector involvement is inconsistent.¹⁸ As Sutherland points out:

In South Africa, the legal and policy frameworks for infrastructure have been problematic, with changes being made slowly, with poor quality drafting and inadequate parliamentary scrutiny of legislation, weak regulation, and excessive reliance on poorly controlled and financed state-owned enterprises (SOEs). In telecommunications, the government failed to make Telkom SA comply with its pro-competitive policies, despite it being both state-owned and regulated. Corruption badly affected the monopoly electricity generator and railway company, while SAA and SABC were made all but bankrupt. Data protection legislation has only recently and partially become operational, after two decades of preparation, leaving it far behind developments in Europe, though still ahead of much of Africa. Cybersecurity has received some attention, but with government adopting overly complex policies and mechanisms for inter-departmental and inter-governmental cooperation, while legislation has made only slow progress. The education system cannot produce sufficient graduates in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) to meet demand, largely because there are too few appropriately qualified school leavers. Nor are there adequate systems to train and re-train individuals in information and communication technology (ICT) skills. While there has been progress in the creation of technology hubs and financing for start-ups, these have yet to have a significant economic effect.¹⁹

The NDP 2030 was adopted as an action plan to address these issues, and to enable the government and the country to take advantage of rapid technological changes.²⁰ As the introductory chapter of this volume rightly notes, AI may be perceived as powerful computer

¹⁶ Mncayi P and Meyer FD 'Evaluating the Determinants of the Perceptions of Underemployment among Young University Graduates: A South African University case' *Cogent Social Sciences* (2022), 8(1):2054126; der Berg S, V., & Gustafsson, M. (2019). Educational outcomes in Post-apartheid South Africa: Signs of progress despite great inequality. In N. Spaul & J. D. Jansen (Eds.), *South African schooling: The enigma of inequality: A study of the present situation and future possibilities* (pp. 25–45). Springer; Stats SA (Statistics South Africa). (2020). *Labour market dynamics survey, 2018*. Government Printer; Stats SA (Statistics South Africa). 2021. *Youth still find it difficult to secure jobs in South Africa*. <http://www.statssa.gov.za/?p=14415> (accessed 13 June 2023); Tewari DD 'Is matric math a good predictor of a student's performance in the first year of a university degree? A case study of faculty of management studies, University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa' *International Journal of Educational Sciences*, (2014) 6(2), 233–237; deLange J 'What are the reasons for unemployment in South Africa?' (15 March 2023) <<https://briefly.co.za/facts-lifefacks/services/155202-what-reasons-unemployment-south-africa-2023/>>

¹⁷ Block D, Laxton DM, Zvikomborero B, Kamohi L, Ramashia F, Kanwa L, Mashatola SN, Bob TK, Moyo T, Semanya A, Van Der Westhuizen B 'The Impact of Poor Policy Implementation by the Government of the Republic of South Africa of Service Delivery' *Reginsights* (4 July 2020) <<https://www.regenesys.net/reginsights/the-impact-of-poor-policy-implementation-by-the-government-of-the-republic-of-south-africa-on-service-delivery/>>.

¹⁸ Sutherland, E., 2020. The fourth industrial revolution—the case of South Africa. *Politikon*, 47(2), p.234. See also Makulilo, A.B., 2016. The context of data privacy in Africa. In *African data privacy laws* (pp. 3-23). Springer, Cham; Bayen, M., and Giuliani, D., 2018. 'Africa: A Look at the 442 Active Tech Hubs of the Continent'. <<https://www.gsma.com/mobilefordevelopment/blog-2/africa-a-look-at-the-442-active-tech-hubs-of-the-continent/>>.

¹⁹ See Sutherland, E., 2020. The fourth industrial revolution—the case of South Africa. *Politikon*, 47(2), p.235.

²⁰ Ibid.

systems or machines that have through machine learning, neural networks, logic programming and other techniques, developed human-like capabilities over time.²¹ The list of opportunities that AI can harness and the challenges that AI can be used to address continue to rise. On the African continent, including in South Africa, AI has presented numerous benefits. In Kenya, AI is being used to address some of the issues that prevent financial institutions from lending to smallholder farmers and to interface with weather conditions to assist farmers with making sowing and harvesting decisions.²² Across the African continent and the world, AI continues to find diverse use cases in the healthcare sector, enabling better diagnostics and detection and improving access to medical and treatment providers.²³ In the education sector, AI finds application in grading; tutoring including providing assistance through individualized tutoring for learners with learning difficulties.²⁴ Government and public services are not left out. AI can and has found application in reducing backlogs; lack of accuracy and slow response times in the provision of public services.²⁵ In the life sciences, it helps practitioners diagnose better and to check the efficacy of drugs.²⁶

However, there is another side to AI systems beyond their many benefits. AI systems are considered 'dual use' – capable of being deployed both for beneficial and malign purposes. Apart from its beneficial uses highlighted above, AI systems have the ability to be and have been deployed for malign purposes.²⁷ Not only is AI dual use but it is built in many cases on open source and publicly accessible data.²⁸ Given its dual use and often open source nature, AI systems can challenge national security in unprecedented ways. It has been shown that AI-

²¹ See Chapter 1 of this volume.

²² Pillay, N., 2020. Artificial intelligence for Africa: An opportunity for growth, development, and democratization, p. 9.

²³ Pillay, N., 2020. Artificial intelligence for Africa: An opportunity for growth, development, and democratization, p. 10.

²⁴ Pillay, N., 2020. Artificial intelligence for Africa: An opportunity for growth, development, and democratization, p. 14.

²⁵ Pillay, N., 2020. Artificial intelligence for Africa: An opportunity for growth, development, and democratization, p. 11.

²⁶ Manzi, J., and Scott, S., (2019). 'AI for Life Sciences: What is it Good For?' < <https://foundry.ai/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Foundry.ai-White-Paper-Life-Sciences-Digital.pdf>>

²⁷ Jarrahi MH 'In the Age of the Smart Artificial Intelligence: AI's Dual Capacities for Automating and Informating Work' *Business Information Review* 36:4 (2019), 178 at 180-181; Wilkens U 'Artificial intelligence in the workplace – A double-edged sword' *The International Journal of Information and Learning Technology* 37:5 (2020) 253 at 255.

²⁸ Eckart de Castilho R, Margoni T, Dore G & Labropoulou P 2018 'A Legal Perspective on Training Models for Natural Language Processing' Available at: <<https://aclanthology.org/L18-1202.pdf>> accessed 10 May 2023.

enabled disinformation attacks can be used to create dissent within countries and interference with democratic processes.²⁹ AI software can be paired with other materials to create “smart” weapons. Essentially, AI is a weaponizable technology. Placed in the hands of unscrupulous entities whether deliberately or inadvertently, AI can be used as a tool of or for repression, harm and other malign purposes. Due to its ability to produce and manipulate original content be it text, images, audio and video (for example through deep fakes), AI can be deployed towards information-based operations for good as stated above or for ill (e.g. to spread malign information or misinformation as seen in the efforts of Russia to undermine US elections).³⁰ AI can power data analytics in ways that transform the relationship between companies and consumers and between governments and citizens.³¹ In this environment, data is the new gold and has been used to deliver targeted ads to consumers.³² Again, in the hands of malevolent entities, AI-driven analytics can offer a wicked tool for governments to spy on their citizens and on citizens of other countries, threatening their national security in diverse ways.³³

AI-generated malware has the ability to change at an alarming rate once deployed on a computer system. This makes cyber-attacks more effective than ever before.³⁴ Furthermore, due to its enormous potential, AI systems are vulnerable to attack from competitors and other

²⁹ Okorie, C., 2022. Technology and national security: what’s IP got to with it?. *Journal of Intellectual Property Law and Practice*, 17(8), pp.601-602. Garon, J.M., 2022. When AI Goes to War: Corporate Accountability for Virtual Mass Disinformation, Algorithmic Atrocities, and Synthetic Propaganda. *N. Ky. L. Rev.*, 49, p.181.

³⁰ Alina Polyakova, ‘Weapons of the weak: Russia and AI-driven asymmetric warfare’ 15 November 2018 *Brookings* <<https://www.brookings.edu/articles/weapons-of-the-weak-russia-and-ai-driven-asymmetric-warfare/>>.

³¹ Pappas IO, Mikalef P, Giannakos MN, Krogstie J and Lekakos G. ‘Big Data and Business Analytics Ecosystems: Paving the way towards Digital Transformation and Sustainable Societies’ 2018 (16) *Information Systems and e-Business Management* 16 (2018) 479 at 484 & 486.

³² Akter S, Katina M, Uddin Rajib M, McCarthy G and Rahman M ‘Transforming Business using Digital Innovations: the Application of AI, Blockchain, Cloud and Data Analytics’ *Annals of Operations Research* 308 (2020), 7 at 15; Noort GV, Himelboim It, Martin J and Collinger T, ‘Introducing a Model of Automated Brand-Generated Content in an Era of Computational Advertising’ *Journal of Advertising* 49:4 (2020), 411 at 416.

³³ Varianos D and Stavrou G ‘Surveillance Infrastructure and Artificial Intelligence: Challenging Democracy and Human Right in China’ *The Cyprus Journal of Sciences* 20 (2022), 27 at 31 (presenting evidence of the Chinese Government’s use of AI to interfere in the daily lives of citizens and assume control of their information).

³⁴ Brundage M, Avin S, Clark J, Toner H, Eckersley P, Garfinkel B, Dafoe A, Scharre P, Zeitzoff T, Filar B, Anderson H, Roff H, Allen GC, Steinhardt J, Flynn C, hÉigeartaigh ÓS, Beard S, Belfield H, Farquhar S, Lyle C, Crootof R, Evans O, Page M, Bryson JJ, Yampolskiy VR and Amodei D. ‘The Malicious Use of Artificial Intelligence: Forecasting, Prevention, and Mitigation.’ *ArXiv* (2018), at 18 - 20.

governments.³⁵ This necessitates the idea of laws and policies to help protect AI systems from such attacks.³⁶ In the field of biotechnology, AI can be combined with other innovations to provide solutions that improve human health, food production and environmental sustainability.³⁷ AI can also enable a pathogen to be engineered for lethal purposes.³⁸ This dual use nature of AI necessitates a multi-pronged legislative and policy approach within the intellectual property legal framework.

From the foregoing, the perspective of AI that this chapter is focused on and one that is arguably most relevant and more pertinent for the African continent and for the actualisation of the objectives and priorities of the NDP 2030, is AI as tools (so-called AI applications).³⁹ Essentially, AI is a technology to be understood and leveraged upon for national development. In this regard, the manner in which AI and any other technology is built, introduced, used and/or applied determines its impact and what is imperative is to make inventions and innovations available to the public so that people may build on it responsibly.⁴⁰ How does AI as tools interact with the IP system? The follow-on question which Part III explores is the details of AI applications/deployment/use and how that interacts with the IP system.

³⁵ Moran R. C, Burton J, & Christou G 'The US Intelligence Community, Global Security, and AI: From Secret Intelligence to Smart Spying' *Journal of Global Security Studies* 8:2 (2022), at 11 (arguing that spies could be placed in universities to steal IP relating to AI technologies).

³⁶ Comiter M 'Attacking Artificial Intelligence: AI's Security Vulnerability and What Policymakers Can Do About It' *Belfer Center for Science and International Affairs*, (August 2019)|, at 55.

³⁷ Bedoya GM, Montoya RD, Tabilo-Munizaga G, Pérez-Won M, Lemus-Mondaca R, 'Promising Perspectives on Novel Protein Food Sources Combining Artificial Intelligence and 3D Food Printing for Food Industry' *Trends in Food Science & Technology* 128 (2022) 38 at 44 – 45; Javaid M, Haleem A, Singh PR, Suman R, Gonzalez SE 'Understanding the adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies in improving environmental sustainability' *Sustainable Operations and Computers* 3 (2022) 203 at 206-207.

³⁸ Kavanagh C 'New Tech, New Threats, and New Governance Challenges: an Opportunity to Craft Smarter Responses?' *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace* (2019) at 25.

³⁹ "The Commission: (2) urges State Parties to ensure that all AI technologies, robotics and other new and emerging technologies that are imported from other continents are made applicable to the African context and or adjusted to fit Africa's needs, and to give serious consideration to African values and norms in formulation of AI governance frameworks to address the global epistemic injustice that currently exists". See 473 Resolution on the need to undertake a Study on human and peoples' rights and artificial intelligence (AI), robotics and other new and emerging technologies in Africa - ACHPR/Res. 473 (EXT.OS/ XXXI) 2021 - The African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights (Commission) meeting at its 31st Extraordinary Session held virtually, from 19 to 25 February 2021. See also, Duque Lizarralde, M. and Contreras, H.A., 2022. The real role of AI in patent law debates. *International Journal of Law and Information Technology*, 30(1), pp.23-46; Manzi, J., and Scott, S., (2019). 'AI for Life Sciences: What is it Good For?' < <https://foundry.ai/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Foundry.ai-White-Paper-Life-Sciences-Digital.pdf>>

⁴⁰ Levendowski, A., 2018. How copyright law can fix artificial intelligence's implicit bias problem. *Wash. L. Rev.*, 93, p.579.

III. AI's application to intellectual property law

AI does not exist in a vacuum. It is developed and deployed based on the context of the future; present challenges; objectives and anticipated goals. Developing or creating AI systems involve building machines that can make decisions to achieve a specific purpose and such machines need a knowledge dataset to do so.⁴¹ The data in/for this dataset range from information (e.g., banking history, purchase history, etc.) to images to language in text and spoken form.⁴² These data are then curated and analysed by AI and for AI tools. Globally, including on the African continent, the challenge with creating and curating this dataset is primarily with data access. IP law – particularly, copyright law is considered as restrictive to data access due to the fact that many data sources (i.e., written texts, images, spoken word, etc.) are subjects of IP rights. To avoid liability for copyright infringement, AI developers utilize all or any of the following options: use open source and/or freely available data,⁴³ which may be biased; to build systems to collect data and/or; purchase data access.⁴⁴ However, this poses its own problem of 'implicit bias' in AI systems and applications/use and power concentration in the hands of a few who can purchase data or build systems for data collection.⁴⁵ Data access is also a challenge for AI use, which may exacerbate the use of biased data which in turn could result in biased AI tools and AI applications.⁴⁶

Even with the availability of and access to open access data in various knowledge bases, the absence of or low availability of data/text in African languages makes open access data problematic beyond the general problem of "implicit bias" arising from open access works or materials.⁴⁷ Beyond the challenge of low quantity and quality of data is the issue of the type of data – African languages are not readily available for use in the development and building

⁴¹ Marivate, Vukosi. "Why African natural language processing now? A view from South Africa# AfricaNLP." (2020), p. 3. Brodie, M.L. and Mylopoulos, J. 2012. *On Knowledge Base Management Systems: Integrating Artificial Intelligence and Database Technologies*. Springer Science & Business Media.

⁴² Marivate, Vukosi. "Why African natural language processing now? A view from South Africa# AfricaNLP." (2020), p. 4.; Levendowski p. 590; 593-594.

⁴³ Ncube and Rutenberg See p. 404; Mohamed, S. 4 August 2019. '#Sautiyetu: Raising our voice in artificial intelligence'. Deep Learning Indaba Blog. <https://deeplearningindaba.com/blog/2019/08/sautiyetu-raising-our-voice-in-artificial-intelligence/>, accessed 27 June 2020.

⁴⁴ Levendowski p. 589; 606-608.

⁴⁵ Ibid.

⁴⁶ Levendowski p. 583.

⁴⁷ Marivate, Vukosi. "Why African natural language processing now? A view from South Africa# AfricaNLP." (2020), p. 9. Toyama, K. 2016. 'The internet and inequality', *Communications of the ACM*, 28–30. doi:10.1145/2892557. Levendowski

of machine learning systems.⁴⁸ The fact that current machine learning for AI privileges foreign and European languages over African languages exacerbates the inequalities and social exclusion that national development plans such as the NDP 2030 seeks to address.⁴⁹ If the IP system is to support the development, use and application of AI in Africa, it must enable data access, data curation and responsible use and application of AI.

Another area of concern is in patent law. Generally, patents are awarded for inventions that are patentable within the meaning of the relevant patents statute, are novel, involve an inventive step and are capable of industrial application. In making patent applications, applicants must disclose their patent claims, showing technical information that would be used to examine and authenticate those claims.⁵⁰ In this regard, patent applications and patent documents generally can signal innovations in AI and other technologies. Through patent documents, interested members of the public can find technical information regarding innovation in any field.⁵¹ This may then lead to technology transfer transactions, technology exchange arrangements and other forms of business arrangements that permit the acquisition of technology. They could also lead to the disclosure of information that may be deployed for malign purposes.⁵² This requires thinking about how the IP system could secure, regulate and manage such disclosures.

In focusing on the foregoing aspects of the IP system, one is mindful of the fact that these are neither the only questions in the debate nor the sole focus of the IP system itself. Even if only in relation to AI applications or using AI as tools, various lines of enquiry emerge. Ncube and Rutenberg highlight such normative questions, such as whether AI-generated inventions should be excluded from patent-eligibility; whether it is necessary to revise patentability criteria; how the originality of AI-generated work should be evaluated; whether the list of

⁴⁸ Marivate, Vukosi. "Why African natural language processing now? A view from South Africa# AfricaNLP." (2020), p. 2.

⁴⁹ Marivate, Vukosi. "Why African natural language processing now? A view from South Africa# AfricaNLP." (2020), p. 8.

⁵⁰ See for example, South Africa's Patent Regulations, 1978, as amended.

⁵¹ See Fromer, J.C., 2008. Patent disclosure. *Iowa L. Rev.*, 94, pp. 548-551.

⁵² See Seymore, S.B., 2009. The teaching function of patents. *Notre Dame L. Rev.*, 85, p.621 arguing that, "Because patents can, at times, communicate knowledge as well as, or better than, other information sources, patents could become a competitive source of technical information".

works that are eligible for copyright protection should be revised to allow for various forms of AI-generated works; etc.⁵³ In many jurisdictions, patents statutes do not explicitly exclude or include advanced and emerging technologies in its list of patentable inventions, and so, such technologies may be patentable if they meet the three eligibility criteria – if they are new, involve an inventive step and are capable of industrial application.⁵⁴ In assessing the presence of these criteria, patent examiners check, amongst other things, whether or not the claimed invention is obvious to a “person skilled in the art” within which such invention falls. For AI-generated inventions in particular, it has been suggested that patent examiners need to upgrade their systems to deploy AI in patent examinations as relying solely on human examiners may be challenging for examining such patents. As the US Patent and Trademark Office pointed out, “AI systems can be trained to analyse patent applications and identify inconsistencies, inaccuracies, or prior art that may render an invention unpatentable [which] can improve the accuracy of patent grants by identifying problematic applications more quickly”.⁵⁵ However, in many countries in Africa, there is currently no mechanism in place for substantive examination of patents.⁵⁶ Instead, the current patent application system operates as a repository system and patent officials undertake mainly formal examination – assessing patent application for compliance with form and filing requirements.

Beyond innovations that fall within the criteria for IP protection, there are technological and/or technical know-how, business secrets, etc. that, while valuable, may either not satisfy IP protection criteria or do not fall into the main IPRs. Such know-how may be protected through laws relating to trade secrets, confidential information, and unfair competition. However, explicit trade secrets protection is currently lacking in many African countries. In the absence of specific trade secret protection laws, it is common practice for parties to enter into non-disclosure agreements, confidentiality agreements and/or non-compete agreements to protect such information or know-how on an ongoing basis or before the

⁵³ Ncube and Rutenberg (2021) pp. 399-401.

⁵⁴ See Section 1 of the (Nigeria) Patents and Designs Act; s25(1) South Africa Patents Act 57 of 1978 as amended.

⁵⁵ Power Patent ‘USPTO Deploys Numerous AI Tools to Aid Patent and Trademark Examination’ (13 February 2023) <[⁵⁶ Mgbeoji, I., 2014. African patent offices not fit for purpose. *Innovation & Intellectual Property: Collaborative Dynamics in Africa*, pp.234-247.](https://powerpatent.com/blog/uspto-deploys-numerous-ai-tools-to-aid-patent-and-trademark-examination#:~:text=Patent%20Examination%3A%20AI-powered%20systems%20can%20assist%20examiners%20in,process%20and%20improve%20the%20accuracy%20of%20patent%20grants.></p></div><div data-bbox=)

disclosure of such information or know-how. There is ample protection of contracts through the courts and other dispute resolution mechanisms.

In spite of these, the perspective of AI as tools to be used across various sectors and aspects of the society in South Africa and everywhere else in Africa is evidently more useful for IP policymakers, allowing them to focus on using the IP system to enable AI applications.⁵⁷ Viewed in this light, the IP legal framework becomes a system that contributes to AI development, use and application in a manner that benefits African countries and African societies. Moreover, apart from the fact that the use of AI as tools is more pertinent for the actualisation of the objectives and priorities of the NDP 2030, the question of AI as legal subjects is one for legislative reform at least from the perspective of authorship, inventorship and ownership (and the consequent enjoyment) of IP rights. This is so because the current IP statutes and even, national Constitutions do not presently stipulate (or envisage) non-natural and non-juristic persons as authors or inventors.⁵⁸ The same goes for AI-generated outputs in many respects. As recent as 2021, when South Africa's Companies and Intellectual Property Commission (CIPC) awarded a patent for an invention that names an AI system as inventor,⁵⁹ the debate was around the issue of whether the relevant IP laws such as copyright and patent laws in Africa and elsewhere permit and/or envisage non-human authors or inventors.⁶⁰ In this regard, several scholars have pointed out that the copyright and patent legal frameworks are not currently designed to recognise AI as authors in the case of copyright works or as inventors or person skilled in the art in the case of patentable inventions.⁶¹ Others have gone

⁵⁷ See Sutherland, E., 2020. The fourth industrial revolution—the case of South Africa. *Politikon*, 47(2), p. 246.

⁵⁸ See Okorie, C., 2021. 'Artificial Intelligence Systems as Inventor in South African patent system: The case of DABUS'. <<https://ipkitten.blogspot.com/2021/08/artificial-intelligence-system-as.html>>, Oriakhogba, D.O., 2021. What If DABUS Came to Africa? Visiting AI Inventorship and Ownership of Patent from the Nigerian Perspective. *Business Law Review*, 42(2), pp. 89-99; Oriakhogba, D.O., 2021. DABUS gains territory in South Africa and Australia: Revisiting the AI-inventorship question. *South African Intellectual Property Law Journal*, 9(1), pp.87-108.

⁵⁹ See 'SA becomes the first country in the world to award a patent to an AI-generated invention' (03 August 2021) <<https://www.businessinsider.co.za/south-africa-first-in-the-world-to-award-an-ai-patent-2021-8>>.

⁶⁰ See Oriakhogba D., 2021 'DABUS gains territory in South Africa and Australia: Revisiting the AI-inventorship question'. *South African Intellectual Property Law Journal*, 9(1), pp.87-108; Okorie, C., 2021. 'Artificial Intelligence Systems as Inventor in South African patent system: The case of DABUS'. <<https://ipkitten.blogspot.com/2021/08/artificial-intelligence-system-as.html>>.

⁶¹ George, A. and Walsh, T., 2022. Artificial intelligence is breaking patent law. *Nature*, 605(7911), pp.616-618. Pp. 616-617. DABUS gains territory in South Africa and Australia: Revisiting the AI-inventorship question. *South African Intellectual Property Law Journal*, 9(1), pp.87-108.

as far as arguing that even if the current IP framework could be expanded or interpreted to accommodate AI as authors or inventors, the IP framework should not.⁶² Yet, for other groups, companies (and non-humans such as AI) can be inventors and authors because corporations are the users of trade secrets, owners and users of trade marks, and authors for certain works created by their employees or which they made arrangements for; etc.⁶³

More importantly, the real issue of concern presently is or should be how the IP system can promote the use of AI as a tool for national development. As seen from other jurisdictions (and continents), IP rule-making when it comes to AI, has become a question of political ideology. Different jurisdictions are also now competing on regulatory and governance frameworks on AI and the role of IP is a particular area of focus and interest. Part IV attempts a response to this follow-on question of how those IP systems may be deployed to make AI work for the African continent.

IV. *I ma nju oguga; ju ochicha*: Intellectual property should not restrict innovations in AI

Having established the link between AI and specific areas of copyright, patents and in more limited fashion, trade secret laws as well as the IP law challenges that derail Africa from harnessing the benefits of AI and challenges posed by AI to Africa's context, this section suggests how those IP systems may be deployed to make AI work for the African continent.

Sometimes a system can do more by getting out of the way than by trying to actively undertake specific tasks. This is the sentiment behind the Igbo language adage, "*i ma nju oguga; ju ochicha*" (literal translation: You cannot refuse to move and also refuse to get out of the way). IP rights/protection are only one part of the IP system. Copyright law is about a bundle of exclusive rights granted to authors and owners of designated protectable subject matters. It is also about the scope of the rights, the scope of the designated protectable

⁶² Gervais – Human cause.

⁶³ See Crouch, D., 2022. 'Legal fictions and the corporation as an inventive artificial intelligence' In *Research Handbook on Intellectual Property and Digital Technologies*. Edward Elgar Publishing; Scannell, B., 2022. When Irish AIs are smiling: could Ireland's legislative approach be a model for resolving AI authorship for EU member states?. *Journal of Intellectual Property Law and Practice*, 17(9), pp.727-740; Thaldar, D. and Naidoo, M., 2021. AI inventorship: The right decision?. *South African Journal of Science*, 117(11-12), pp.1-3.

subject matters and the exceptions to the application of the exclusive rights.⁶⁴ In the same vein, patents law is about both the exclusive rights of patentees and the exceptions and limitations to the scope of those exclusive rights.⁶⁵ By extension, the grant of IP rights or protection to AI as tools is not the only way (and may not be the most appropriate way) for Africa to take advantage of the opportunities, and overcome the challenges, of AI on the continent.⁶⁶

Apart from granting a bundle of exclusive rights to authors and/or copyright owners, copyright law has certain inbuilt mechanisms to promote access to copyright-protectable subject matter which may constitute data for AI development. These mechanisms are in the form of copyright limitations and exceptions which may be applied to several purposes from promoting authorship; protecting consumer interests; fulfilling social policy goals to fostering innovation and addressing market failure problems.⁶⁷ Already, the fair use doctrine that holds sway in the United States has been proposed as a panacea to address data access and implicit bias in data for AI development. Arguing that AI's use of data meets all the relevant factors to determine if a particular use of protectable subject matter is fair, many scholars argue that the fair use doctrine can help solve the AI bias problem by increasing AI's access to more (and varied) data.⁶⁸ Levendowski suggests that the US fair use doctrine is one area of copyright law that may be applied successfully to address concerns of data access in the context of AI.⁶⁹ Within South Africa, such proposals are used to provide support for recommending the adoption of a US-style fair use copyright exception within the current copyright statutory reform process.⁷⁰ Beyond the statutory amendment process, South Africa's Constitutional

⁶⁴ Elkin Koren, N., 2017. Copyright in a digital ecosystem: a user-rights approach. In: R. Okediji, ed., *Copyright Law in an Age of Limitations and Exceptions*. Cambridge University Press, pp.132-168.

⁶⁵ See Jegede, O. and Ncube, C., 2021. Science, Technology, Innovation Management for Industrial Development in South Africa: Implications for The Fourth Industrial Revolution. *Science*, 15(9), pp. 682-683; 686.

⁶⁶ See Jegede, O. and Ncube, C., 2021. Science, Technology, Innovation Management for Industrial Development in South Africa: Implications for The Fourth Industrial Revolution. *Science*, 15(9), pp.673-695. See pp. 682-683.

⁶⁷ Samuelson, P., 2017. Justifications for Copyright Limitations & Exceptions . In R. Okediji, ed., *Copyright Law in an Age of Limitations and Exceptions*. Cambridge University Press, pp. 12-59.

⁶⁸ Levendowski 622-629. Ncube and Rutenberg See p. 404; Mohamed, S. 4 August 2019. '#Sautiyetu: Raising our voice in artificial intelligence'. Deep Learning Indaba Blog. <https://deeplearningindaba.com/blog/2019/08/sautiyetu-raising-our-voice-in-artificial-intelligence/>, accessed 27 June 2020.

⁶⁹ Levendowski p. 589;

⁷⁰ See Okorie, C., 2021. Long walk to copyright reform (Pt 2): South Africa's National Assembly rescinds its decision to pass the Copyright Amendment Bill <<https://ipkitten.blogspot.com/2021/05/long-walk-to-copyright->

Court recently issued a decision that exemplifies how copyright exceptions could address data access issues. In *Blind SA v Minister of Trade, Industry and Competition and Others*, the Constitutional Court confirmed that to the extent that the Copyright Act 98 of 1978 as amended does not permit the reproduction and adaptation of copyright-protected literary and artistic works in accessible format for the use of visually-impaired persons, it was unconstitutional.⁷¹ The Constitutional Court further directed the reading in of a new s13A into the Copyright Act. Section 13A is geared towards making specified copyright-protected works available to persons with visual disabilities. It defines ‘accessible format copy’ to mean a copy of a work that gives visually impaired persons access to the work as “feasibly and comfortably” as a person without such disability and envisages only literary works and artistic works forming part of a literary work.⁷² While the Constitutional Court decision focuses specifically on visually impaired persons, there are elements in the larger picture of the Copyright Amendment Bill in South Africa to suggest that permitting the making of accessible format copy may become a norm that will benefit South Africa including and even in the AI space. As Marivate points out, a practice as simple as publishing documents in plain text as opposed to PDFs can make it more accessible to machines and not just humans.⁷³

AI is open innovation with firms using both external and internal ideas and know-how in its development and deployment,⁷⁴ and this manner in which AI is developed, used and applied is important. If the IP system is to address the dual use nature of AI and help prevent its malevolent development, use and application in Africa, it must be applied in a manner that necessitates responsible use and application of AI. As suggested above, disclosures in patent claims may be problematic where they bring about knowledge transfer of malign uses of AI without an accompanying measure of control and/or responsibility. Currently, the statutory provisions on inventions that may have such dual use or that may involve such problematic disclosures (or disclosures generally) are quite vague. For example, s4 of Nigeria’s Patents and

reform-pt-2.html>. cf. Elkin-Koren, N. and Netanel, N.W., 2020. Transplanting fair use across the globe: A case study testing the credibility of US opposition. *Hastings LJ*, 72, p.1121.

⁷¹ (CCT 320/21) [2022] ZACC 33 (21 September 2022).

⁷² *Blind SA v Minister of Trade, Industry and Competition and Others*, supra at para. 6.

⁷³ Marivate, Vukosi. "Why African natural language processing now? A view from South Africa# AfricaNLP." (2020), p. 15.

⁷⁴ Zhang B, Wang H 'Network Proximity Evolution of Open Innovation Diffusion: A Case of Artificial Intelligence for Healthcare' *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity* 7: 222 (2021), at 10 – 11.

Designs Act 2004 stipulates that patents cannot validly be obtained for inventions whose publication or exploitation would be contrary to public order or morality.⁷⁵ No definition is proffered for what kind of publication or exploitation would be contrary to public order but the Act indicates that the fact that the exploitation of a patent is prohibited by law does not necessarily translate to such invention being contrary to public order. In the case of South Africa, s25(4) of the Patents Act provides that “a patent shall not be granted for an invention the publication of which would be generally expected to encourage offensive or immoral behaviour”. Section 36(1)(b) goes on to empower the Registrar of Patents to refuse a patent application where it appears to the Registrar that “the use of the invention to which the application relates would be generally expected to encourage offensive or immoral behaviour”. Under s36(2), the registrar may also refuse a patent application where it appears to him that the invention in respect of which the patent application is made might be used in a manner contrary to law unless the applicant amends the specification to include relevant disclaimers as to the illegality. These statutory provisions lead to at least three possibilities: (i) the grant or non-grant of patent can be used as a tool to control the publication of inventions that are deemed contrary to public order or morality or deemed offensive. This could apply to sensitive, weaponizable technologies including AI; (ii) a patent may be granted for such inventions but its exploitation prohibited by law and (iii) the discretion of the Registrar (at least in the case of South Africa) may be a tool to refuse AI patent applications that may be problematic. These possibilities should form the basis as to how African countries should reform their respective patent systems to undertake substantive examinations in a manner that caters for innovations in AI and other emerging technologies; how to design a publication and disclosure system that would adequately cater for innovations in AI to dissuade diversion for malign purposes. The possibilities should also inform the design of systems to encourage disclosure of inventions to government even where the prohibition of exploitation or refusal of patents is likely.

Where the patents system is problematic (and sometimes, despite the availability of patents protection), trade secrets and contractual protection confidential information are the go-to protection/ownership systems for innovations involving AI applications/tools. In such cases

⁷⁵ Section 13 makes a similar provision in the case of industrial designs.

and unlike the patent system, there is little or no access to technical knowledge in the public domain regarding such innovations. Also, the fact that trade secrets and technical know-how are currently protected through contracts can be problematic. Contracts are not necessarily secure protection means. Moreover, to the extent that there are no disclosures, sensitive technologies may be transferred to malevolent third parties without government's knowledge. To address this issue, it may be helpful to provide explicit statutory protection for trade secrets, which would indicate thresholds for disclosure of trade secrets to governments and require government action to guarantee confidentiality of information disclosed to it.

There is a growing movement within the IP and text and data mining fields to recognise and enforce a right to research as a human right.⁷⁶ Such right to research in the case of African countries has both constitutional underpinnings and IP rights (especially, copyright) exceptions.⁷⁷ According to Oriakhogba, "the right to research will lead to the enshrinement of a positive user right that will confer researchers (including authors), libraries and archives the capacity to protect and enforce a right of access to information covered by copyright...[i]t will also solve the copyright exclusivity challenge to text and data mining within the African context".⁷⁸ While the enshrinement of a right to research that correlates with IP rights is a worthy step towards ensuring that IP rights do not get in the way of AI in Africa, the question of its implementation remains. As suggested elsewhere, access-promoting systems and/or solutions must go beyond legislative solutions and judicial interpretation and focus on *how* (best) to ensure the practical application, implementation and/or utilisation of such solutions.⁷⁹ To address this issue in relation to promoting the development and deployment of AI as tools, government-backed activities in the form of explainers, guidance notes, press

⁷⁶ See Flynn, S., Schirru, L.,; Palmedo, M., and Izquierdo, A., 2022 'Research Exceptions in Comparative Copyright.' PIJIP/TLS Research Paper Series no. 75. <https://digitalcommons.wcl.american.edu/research/75>; Geiger, C., 2021. 'The Missing Goal-Scorers in the Artificial Intelligence Team: Of Big Data, the Fundamental Right to Research and the failed Text and Data Mining limitations in the CSDM Directive.' PIJIP/TLS Research Paper Series no. 66. <https://digitalcommons.wcl.american.edu/research/66>

⁷⁷ Oriakhogba, D.O., 2022. The Right to Research in Africa: Making African Copyright Whole. Joint PIJIP/TLS Research Paper Series, p. 39.

⁷⁸ Oriakhogba R2R p.18.

⁷⁹ See the discussion in Okorie, Cl. 'Fair use or fair dealing in Africa: The South African experience', in H Boshier – E Rosati (eds), *Developments and Directions in Intellectual Property Law. 20 Years of The IPKat* (OUP: in press), Chapter 17.

releases, etc.⁸⁰ and active citizen participation from AI developer communities may provide practical guidance as to design and customisation of the IP system.⁸¹ That said, there are counter arguments to using copyright exceptions to promote access to data to build AI systems.

In 2023, the UK Government decided that it will not broaden the scope of its copyright limitations and exceptions to cover text and data mining (TDM) to train the AI model. The prevailing reasoning behind such decision was the argument that copyright exceptions to cover TDM will adversely affect the rights holders and possibly destroy the creative industry.⁸² However there was no empirical evidence to suggest that training AI models with TDM would be prejudicial to the creative industry and creators. Moreover, the focus on the debate was limited to copyright, without any or much consideration of patent law. The patent systems could benefit from AI that can reduce the time spent on reading long and complicated patent descriptions to foster innovation and competition. More significantly, the fact that the UK government declined to proceed with TDM exceptions does not mean that the door is forever closed nor does it necessarily follow that Africa should follow the same trajectory.

One aspect of the patent system that could benefit from reforms that would serve to promote AI in Africa is the timing and content of patent disclosures. As stated earlier, the patents system requires that potential patentees file their claim specifications at the time of applying for patents protection. No further disclosures are required beyond this point. Generally, patent disclosures happen before commercialization. Even when it happens after commercialization, there are usually several improvements refinements to the invention

⁸⁰ See UK Intellectual Property Office, 'Examining patent applications relating to artificial intelligence (AI) inventions: The Guidance' (22 September 2022), < <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/examining-patent-applications-relating-to-artificial-intelligence-ai-inventions/examining-patent-applications-relating-to-artificial-intelligence-ai-inventions-the-guidance>>; Okorie, C., 2022. 'Wanjiru v Machakos University: Image rights and its relationship with constitutional/human rights in Kenya' < <https://ipkitten.blogspot.com/2022/09/wanjiru-v-machakos-university-image.html?m=1> >.

⁸¹ As Yu advises in relation to the furore on adoption of fair use, "[P]olicymakers and commentators advocating copyright reform should avoid focusing too much on efforts to transplant fair use. Rather, they should put more time, effort, energy and resources into exploring ways to design or customize fair use". See Peter K. Yu, 'Customizing fair use transplants.' (2018) 7(1) *Laws* 9 (hereafter, Yu 'Transplants'); Niva Elkin-Koren, 'The New Frontiers of User Rights.' (2016) 32 *American University International Law Review* p.11.

⁸² UK Parliament 'Artificial Intelligence: Intellectual Property Rights' 1 February 2023 <<https://hansard.parliament.uk/commons/2023-02-01/debates/7CD1D4F9-7805-4CF0-9698-E28ECEF7177/ArtificialIntelligenceIntellectualPropertyRights>> [accessed: 06 July 2023].

before and during commercialization. These improvements and refinements could come as a result of market testing, products or service distribution, customer feedback, technology transfers, feedback from interactions with government and regulatory authorities, etc.⁸³ The knowledge from these improvements and refinements would of course not be part of the patent disclosures and therefore unknown and secrets and could even be secured and protected as trade secrets. Yet, if one considers one of the key purposes or rationale for patent monopoly - the knowledge disclosed in the patent claims in exchange for a limited monopoly - this “static” disclosure system is problematic. It is even more problematic for dual use inventions such as AI where other areas of AI application may go undetected. There are different suggestions in the literature as to how to address the problem posed by the “static” disclosure system in particular how to move instead to some sort of dynamic patent disclosures to be made post-filing and/or post grant.⁸⁴

Fromer suggests that rather than require patentees to disclose all commercialization information related to their patents post filing, United States law should require a different form of dynamic patent disclosures -patentees should be required to divulge to the patent office all inventions that they or their licensees commercialises.⁸⁵ The benefits of this approach, according to Fromer, are that the public would have a better understanding of the scope of the patent claim and there would be an increase in the purchase of the disclosed products as well as a better understanding of the patent’s contribution to knowledge.⁸⁶ Where AI tools or applications improve the commercialization of a patented invention, a dynamic patent disclosure system can ensure that this information is available to the public. One other benefit of this approach to disclosures is that it provides government and policy makers with an empirical and more systemic understanding of the varied uses and applications of specific inventions and technologies which can in turn lead to understanding foreign interest in and acquisition of AI tools emanating from Africa. This chapter argues that

⁸³ See *Biotech Laboratories (Pty) Ltd v Beecham Group PLC and Another* 2002 (4) SA 249 (SCA) involving package inserts improved based on feedback from the Medicines Control Council.

⁸⁴ Fromer, J.C., 2016. Dynamic patent disclosure. *Vand. L. Rev.*, 69, pp. 1721-1723, Chien, C., 2016. Rethinking Patent Disclosure, *Vand. L. Rev.*, 69, pp. 1849, 1866-72.

⁸⁵ See Fromer, J.C., 2016. Dynamic patent disclosure. *Vand. L. Rev.*, 69, p. 1722.

⁸⁶ See Fromer, J.C., 2016. Dynamic patent disclosure. *Vand. L. Rev.*, 69, p. 1723.

some of these approaches to dynamic disclosures may well serve the opportunities and challenges that AI presents to Africa.

The dynamic patent disclosure approach proposed by Fromer is somewhat similar to the government approval of technology transfer system applicable in Nigeria. Nigeria's National Office for Technology Acquisition and Promotion (*NOTAP*) Act 2004 requires Nigerian companies to seek and obtain the approval of NOTAP for acquisition and transfers of foreign technologies.⁸⁷ Per the recent guidelines published by NOTAP, applicants for approval involving commercialisation of the results of research and development are required to submit a feasibility report of their project with prototypes of their technologies while applicants for technology transfer agreements must submit a draft of the technology agreements.⁸⁸ This regulatory approach enables the State to access some of the benefits of dynamic disclosures.⁸⁹ However, there are certain drawbacks to the current system.

The NOTAP Act is "import-facing" as it focuses on transfer and acquisition of foreign technology into Nigeria and does not (directly) deal with the transfer of Nigeria-developed technology out of the country. Further, where the NOTAP refuses to register an agreement, the relevant Nigerian company will be unable to access official banking channels through which they may pay their foreign investor for technology acquired. The decision of the Nigerian Court of Appeal in *Stanbic IBTC Holdings Plc v Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria & NOTAP*,⁹⁰ confirms that the scope of NOTAP's powers does not extend to technology transfers for exporting technology out of Nigeria. The Court further held that even in the case of technology import, non-registration of contracts with NOTAP does not invalidate or void such contracts. The only effect of failure to register technology transfer contracts is that payments for such technology through or on the authority of the CBN or any licensed Nigerian bank cannot be made. While this decision and its interpretation of the NOTAP Act provides

⁸⁷ See s5(2) of the Act.

⁸⁸ See NOTAP, 'Revised guidelines for registration and monitoring of technology transfer agreements in Nigeria' (February 2020) <https://notap.gov.ng/new_dev/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/notap_tech_trans_agreement_revised_guidelines.pdf>

⁸⁹ Ajibo, C.C., Anozie, M.C., Onyeabor, E., Umahi, T.O., Odinkonigbo, J.J. and Agu, H., 2019. Technology transfer for development in Nigeria: patterns, problems and prospects. *Commonwealth Law Bulletin*, 45(1), pp.70-91.

⁹⁰ (2018) LCN/12169(CA).

some clarification as to NOTAP's statutory role, it has the effect of dissuading registration in the case of technology exchanges. Increasingly, technology transfers go both ways and are increasingly exchanges between parties as opposed to one party transferring to the another. Furthermore, payments and investments for technology are not always in cash. Payments and investments may be in kind and regulatory oversight must devise ways to secure innovation that follow such route.

However, there are other provisions in the NOTAP Act that may be deployed to help the cause of promoting AI development and application. By virtue of ss 1 and 2 of the NOTAP Act, other functions may be conferred on NOTAP pursuant to the Act and the governing body of NOTAP known as the Governing Council of the National Office for Technology Acquisition and Promotion has the powers and responsibility to formulate policy for the NOTAP. These provisions may be utilised to expand NOTAP's policies and functions to include technologies exported from Nigeria. Whether a registration system that applies to all technology exports should be implemented is a different matter entirely. A notification system may be best with a time limit for NOTAP to approve or disapprove and NOTAP equipped with appropriate training to identify red flags in terms of AI dual use concerns and to conduct expedited reviews.

While there are financial costs associated with collecting, curating, and submitting the information required in a dynamic disclosure system, such costs may be offset with benefits or incentives for patentees and AI developers.⁹¹ Furthermore, concerns around how to ensure compliance with the requirements by providing accurate and verifiable data may be ameliorated by providing for penalties or fines for false or misleading information.⁹² Pursuant to s 14 of the NOTAP Act, NOTAP may require companies to furnish information as it (NOTAP) may specify and there are penalties for giving false information.

V. Conclusion

If the intellectual property legal framework is to contribute to harnessing the opportunities and addressing the challenges of AI in Africa, it is crucial to appreciate that the context of the

⁹¹ Fromer, J.C., 2016. Dynamic patent disclosure. *Vand. L. Rev.*, 69, p. 1732.

⁹² Fromer, J.C., 2016. Dynamic patent disclosure. *Vand. L. Rev.*, 69, p. 1734.

continent requires to instead enable AI Development not necessarily with IPRs but by using the IP system to provide an enabling environment for data access, data curation and disclosures. As such, this chapter proposes that delineating and maintaining the scope of and approach to intellectual property protection as well as actualising limitations and exceptions, can help South Africa and other African countries to better utilise AI and meet its development goals and plans and address concerns to national security.

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